

Fabrication of novel zeolite NaA/MgFe₂O₄ nanocomposite catalyst for the effective removal of chemical warfare nerve agent simulant

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Abstract

The aim of present study is to investigate the effective removal of chemical warfare nerve agent simulant dimethyl methyl phosphonate from water solution by the novel zeolite NaA/MgFe₂O₄ nanocomposite catalyst. For the purpose, MgFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully fabricated over the zeolite NaA via the hydrothermal method and identified using FESEM, EDAX, XRD, FTIR and AFM analyses.

The performance of the NaA/MgFe₂O₄ nanocomposite catalyst was then evaluated for the removal (adsorption and degradation) of DMMP agent simulant and monitored by using a GC-FID technique.

Furthermore, the influence of different parameters involving contact time, initial concentration, adsorbent dose, and catalyst type on the removal of DMMP were investigated. The obtained outcomes from GC-FID analysis verified the maximum removal more than 96% for DMMP agent simulant. The parameters including: contact time (40 min), adsorbent dose (0.1 g), and initial concentration (50 mg/L) were gained as the optimized amounts for the removal reaction. Additionally, the non-toxic methyl phosphoric acid (MPA) as the degradation reaction product of the DMMP by the NaA/MgFe₂O₄ catalyst was identified.

Keywords: Zeolite, Chemical warfare, Catalyst, Nerve agent.